

STUDY SKILLS AND ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG GRADE SIX STUDENTS

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Abstract.Elementary students especially those who are in grade six are subjected to a broad variety of pressures in their academics, some of which are more intense than others. Hence, the primary goal of this research is to determine if the indicators of grade six students' study skills significantly influence their academic stress as perceived by their teachers. This study utilized non-experimental quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlation technique. Statistical analysis such as mean, standard deviation, Pearson R correlation and Multiple Linear Regression were used in treating the data generated in the study. The respondents of the study were the 100 sixth-grade educators teaching in Piedad District primary schools in Davao City. These respondents were selected using convenience sampling method. Data were evaluated from the survey questionnaires adopted by the researcher with modification in order to fit to the study which undergone validation from experts and were tested for its reliability. Descriptive results of the study revealed that grade six study skills and academic stress as perceived by their teachers obtained a "high" descriptive level rating which means that students' study skills and academic stress are oftentimes evident. Consequently, the inferential results of the study suggested that it failed to accept its null hypothesis since there is a significant relationship between study skills and academic stress among the grade six students. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that all of the indicators of the grade six students' study skills significantly influenced their academic stress.

KEY WORDS

1. Study Skills. 2. Academic Stress. 3. Grade Six Students.

1. Introduction

It is usual practice to use the phrase "pressure" to characterize responses across the board, including those in the body, the mind, and the behavior. This means that every activity done by a student might be considered to be dangerous or difficult to handle in some way. This can be a good thing for it might transform students to be resilient to external pressures. However, elementary school students especially those who are in grade six are subjected to a broad variety of pressures in their academics, some of

which are more intense than others. This leads to the development of academic stress which affect many of their routine in school such as their study habits which has a direct relationship with their performance in school. Researchers and educative administrators who shape policy have been worried for a very long time about the high levels of academic stress experienced by elementary students. Relatively, there are many different factors that contribute to the high levels of academic stress experienced by elementary stu-

dents. Among these factors are the expectation of self, expectation of parents/teachers, and depression. In addition, it is possible for students to feel or report significant levels of stress which can have a detrimental impact on their study habits, which in turn can have a bad impact on their school academic performance (Kaur Kaur 2015). Specifically, study habits are student's ways of studying whether systematic, efficient or inefficient (Ayodele Adebisi, 2013) implying that efficient study habits such as time management, note taking, reading comprehension skills produces positive academic performance while inefficient study habits lead to academic failure. Globally, students in today's schools are faced with a wide variety of academic demands, including tests, grading assignments, competing with peers, gaining a comprehension of course material, and most of all is the negative effect of COVID-19 pandemic to education or the learning quality during the new normal. Knowing all these factor may lead to frustration due to exhaustion of resources. This phenomenon in which the mental and emotional toll that being a student has on a person is referred to as academic stress (Bisht, 2019). In addition, students may experience academic stress when they perceive that the demands placed on them intellectually exceed their capacity to deal with the situation using their own resources. In other words, the students believe that the situation is beyond their ability to handle using their own resources which is both internal and external (Dhanalakshmi Murty, 2018). Also, expectations that one has on oneself, as well as those that one places on one's parents and teachers, as well as sentiments of melancholy, all contribute to the pressure that one feels to succeed academically. In the Philippines, the IATF imposed a countrywide ban on all public gatherings which had a significant and negative effect on students across the board (Ocampo Yamagishi, 2020).

The Department of Education (DepEd), particularly in public schools, mandated the use of the Modular Distance Learning System (MDL) as a means of keeping the education system current and preventing it from falling behind other government sector. In addition, the educational process went through yet another transformation when the DepEd mandated the usage of the face-to-face learning mode commencing in November 2022 (DepEd, 2022). This unanticipated chain of events has the potential to lead to a broad variety of academic stress for the students. With this, it was tough for them to adapt their study habits and any other types of educational technique due to a variety of different factors (Cabardo, Cabardo, Cabardo-Mabida, 2022). Also, anxiety and academic stress have the potential to have a long-lasting influence on the mental health of primary school students, which, in turn, has the potential to harm the students' study habits and character development (Grande et al., 2021). Although there is growing interest on students' study habits as well as the stress the had encountered during the new normal learning set-up, there are few studies that investigate the relationship between these two components (Cho, Marjadi, Langendyk, Hu, 2017) and most of this studies were conducted during the pre-COVID period. Although there were several studies on these variables, there were only few studies focusing on these two variables. Developing good study habits such as having time management, proper note taking techniques, and reading comprehension are factors that help students to work efficiently which might reduce their academic stress. With this, this study will focus on demonstrating a possible association between study skills and academic stress among grade six students during their face-to-face learning delivery mode after the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods in conducting the study which are considered strategies or techniques utilized in the collection of data evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create better understanding of a topic. Contents of this chapter include the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher used a descriptive correlational strategy for non-experimental quantitative research. The descriptive design explains the researched population, circumstance, or phenomena. It emphasizes on addressing the how, what, when, and where questions rather than the why of a research topic. Quantitative research employs a deductive-inductive technique, which means it departs from a theoretical framework, the idea of experts, and develops issues and their answers based on the researchers' experience and knowledge (Tanzeh, 2011). In particular, this will be used in this study in assessing the extent of study skills and the academic stress of grade six students of the research locale. This design is important to the research because it specifies the techniques and processes for gathering the necessary information, as well as the general operational pattern or framework of the project, which dictates what information is to be acquired from which sources using which methods (Nassaji, 2015). In addition, Grove, Burns, and Gray (2012) noted that descriptive quantitative design may be used to generate theory, uncover difficulties with present practice, defend current practice, make judgments, or determine what others in comparable circumstances are doing.

2.2. Research Respondents—The Piedad District primary schools in Davao City, which are located in the middle part of the city, will serve as the locations of this study. The one hundred (100) sixth-grade educators will serve as responders in this research. The respondents will be selected using the convenience sampling

method. This is considered the most common method of selection that does not rely on probability, will be used to choose them. It is a method for collecting samples that involves getting samples from sources of data that are easily located or that provide researchers convenience (Edgar and Manz, 2017). The researcher will ensure that several criteria will be met in selecting the respondents such as the years a grade six teacher and the age of the respondents.

2.3. Research Instrument—Study Instruments are measuring instruments meant to collect data from research participants on a topic of interest. It must aid in addressing the research's goals, objectives, and research questions, as well as support or refute the study's premise (McMillan Schumacher, 2013). In this investigation, the researcher will use survey questionnaire as its instrument in gathering its data. The survey questionnaire will have two parts that would cater the two variables in the study. In addition, validity of the instrument will be assured by research expert and members of the panel committee. The survey instrument also will be subjected for pilot testing in order to determine its reliability. This will be computed using the value of the instrument's Cronbach's Alpha. For the first part of the survey instrument, this would provide data on the data on the skills of the respondents. Questions from this part of the instrument were adopted from the Study Habits Inventory by Wrenn, Humber McKewon (2005). In the process of interpreting its data, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale with description and interpre-

tation is shown below. The following five order and description were considered: gradations with their respective range of means

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very High	This means that the grade six students’ Study Skills is always evident.
3.40–4.19	High	This means that the Study Skills is oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderate	This means that the Study Skills is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Low	This means that the Study Skills is seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Very Low	This means that the Study Skills is never evident.

For the second part of the questionnaire, (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest in this will determine the extent of of the grade six students’ academic stress. In this part, the researcher adopted from Beck (1988) Expectation and Depression Inventory (MAI). The same with the first part of the survey questionnaire, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five

(5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest in interpreting its data. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Descriptive Levels and Interpretations of Academic Stress

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very High	This means that the grade six students’ Academic Stress is always evident.
3.40–4.19	High	This means that the grade six students’ Academic Stress is oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderate	This means that the grade six students’ Academic Stress is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Low	This means that the grade six students’ Academic Stress is seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Very Low	This means that the grade six students’ Academic Stress is never evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data gathering procedure, the researcher will write a letter seeking permission from the Dean of the Graduate School so that this research study will be conducted. Next, the researcher will secure a letter asking for permission to the Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Davao del Sur through the channels of the Office of Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) of the selected differ-

ent schools. Upon approval of the permit, the survey questionnaire will be ready for the conduct of the study. During the conduct of the study, the researcher will personally hand-in the survey questionnaire to the selected respondents. The questionnaire will be retrieved right after the respondents will be done answering the survey questions. The researcher will en-

sure that the collection and retrieval of data will be conducted following the IATF protocols for face-to-face learning delivery mode. Lastly, the collected data will be analyzed by a statistician using the different measures of treating the data as presented this chapter. The results in the treatment of the data were interpreted for further information of the study.

2.5. Data Analysis—The study will use the respondents' collected data for analysis. The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: The mean is commonly used to measure the central tendency. Central tendency identifies a single value as representative of an entire distribution. It also provides an accurate description of the entire data (Creswell, 2013). In this study, mean will be used to determine the extent of grade six students' study skills in terms of (a) Time Management (b) Note Taking, and (c) Reading Comprehension as well as the extent of academic stress in terms of (a) Expectation of Self (b) Expectation of Parents/Teachers, and (c) Depression. The correlational test is one type of inferential statistics that investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. This statistical test reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two

(or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative (Mukaka, 2012). This study used this type of analysis as hypothesis testing to determine the significant relationship between the grade six students' study skills and academic stress. Multiple linear regression (MLR) is a statistical technique for estimating the relationship among variables which have reason and result relation. The main focus is to analyze the relationship between a dependent variable and independent variable and formulate the linear relation between the dependent and independent variable (Rencher and Christensen, 2012). As a predictive analysis, the multiple linear regression was used to explain the relationship between one continuous dependent variable and two or more independent variables. The independent variables can be continuous or categorical. MLR was used in this study to determine which of the grade six students' study skills indicators significantly influence their academic stress.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions based from the data gathered after the conduct of this study. This includes the interpretation of the data and the repercussions of the findings of the study. The deliberations presented in this chapter are aligned to the statement of the problem cited in the previous chapters of this study. Specifically, the presentation for the results and discussions will start from the extent of study skills among grade six students as perceived by teachers in terms of time management, note taking, and reading comprehension. This will be followed on the presentation of the extent of academic stress among grade six students as perceived by teachers in terms of expectation of self, expectation of parents/teacher, and depression. Next, will be the discussion of the results of the significant relationship between the study skills among grade six students and academic stress among grade six students Lastly, the discussion of the results on

which indicators of teachers’ initiative significantly influence Elementary student’s literacy.

Summary of the Extent of Study Skills among Grade Six Students The statistical result on the extent of study skills among grade six students as perceived by their teachers is shown in Table 1. These study skills are meant to employ one’s mind toward the goal of learning. They were referred as individual’s habit for it is anything that is done on a regular basis and is not treated as an afterthought (Nagaraju, 2014). In addition, the sum total of a person’s study skills may be thought of as their daily, weekly, and monthly actions that are directly or indirectly connected to their academic success (Radha and Muthukumar, 2015). This means that students need to develop more focus and enthusiasm for their studies. A strong motivation to learn, together with full mental and physical faculties, is necessary for the formation of efficient study routines and skills (Tope, 2011).

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Study Skills among Grade Six Students as Perceived by their Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Time Management	3.97	High
Note Taking	3.72	High
Reading Comprehension	3.63	High
Overall	3.77	High

Based on the analysis in Table 1, the overall mean rating of the extent of study skills among grade six students is 3.77. This numerical data result had an equivalent descriptive rating equal to “high” which means that the study skills among grade six students is oftentimes evident. Study skills is a broad topic that encompasses various learning strategies and techniques that students can use to improve their academic performance. Study skills are essential for students of all levels, as they enable learners to effectively manage their time, set goals, and retain information (Eom et al., 2021). Consequently, Cleary et al. (2021) synthesized that study skills interventions had a positive impact on students’ academic performance, with the most effective interventions involving metacognitive strategies, self-regulation, and peer tutoring. Specifically, the “time management” indicator of the study skills among grade six students ranked first with a mean score of 3.97.

This indicates that the time management skill as part of the study skills among grade six students is oftentimes evident as perceived by their teachers. This further denotes that grade six students as perceived by their teachers possessed better on this indicator compared to the other indicators of this study. The concept of time management skills as a critical component of study skills among grade six students is an important area of research. Time management skills can help students develop effective learning strategies, reduce stress and anxiety, and improve academic performance (Aljohani et al., 2022). Moreover, Atkinson et al. (2021) found out that time management interventions had a positive impact on students’ academic performance, with the most effective interventions involving goal-setting, time-tracking, and self-reflection. The “note taking” indicator of the study skills among grade six students ranked second with a mean score of 3.72. Still, the said mean score

rating of this indicator is equivalent to “high” descriptive level which means that the note taking skill as part of the study skills among grade six students is oftentimes evident as perceived by their teachers. The note-taking skill is a critical component of study skills among grade six students. Note-taking skills can help students to actively engage with the material, organize their thoughts, and retain information (McDaniel et al., 2022). In addition, Weng et al. (2021) found out that students who received the note-taking training program had significantly higher note-taking and academic achievement scores than those who did not receive the training. The least indicator of the study skills among grade six students is the “reading comprehension” indi-

cator with a mean score rating equal to 3.63. This indicator is equivalent to “high” descriptive level which means that the reading comprehension as part of the study skills among grade six students is oftentimes evident as perceived by their teachers. Reading comprehension is a vital component of study skills among grade six students. Reading comprehension skills can help students understand and retain information, make connections between ideas, and think critically about the material (Durán et al., 2021). In addition, Zhao et al. (2022) showed that the reading comprehension intervention was effective in improving students’ reading comprehension and vocabulary skills.

Summary of the Extent of Academic Stress of Grade Six Students The statistical result on the extent of academic stress among grade six students as perceived by their teachers is shown in Table 8. These ” refers to the emotional and mental condition a student experiences when they are under constant, excessive strain at school from both external and internal sources (Misra et al., 2019). It is influenced

by a student’s surroundings in many aspects of their lives: at school, at home, in their social ties, and even in their neighborhood (Neseliler et al., 2017). Academic pressure is a constant companion for students from kindergarten (Jayanthi, Thirunavukarasu, Rajkumar, 2015) through college (Gurung et al., 2020) and beyond (Trigueros et al., 2020).

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Academic Stress of Grade Six as Perceived by their Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Expectation of Self	4.00	High
Expectation of Parents/Teachers	3.83	High
Depression	3.83	High
Overall	3.88	High

Based on the analysis in Table 2, the overall mean rating of the extent of academic stress among grade six is 3.88. This numerical data result had an equivalent descriptive rating equal to “high” which means that the academic stress among grade six students is oftentimes evident. High levels of academic stress have been connected to both mental and physical health consequences including depression, anxiety, nervousness, and stress-related disorders, all of which can have a detrimental effect on a student’s performance in the classroom (Waqas et al., 2015). Anxiety problems affect about 8Specifically, the “expectation of self” indicator of the academic stress among grade six students ranked first with a mean score of 4.00. This indicates that the “expectation of self” indicator as part of the academic stress among grade six students is oftentimes evident as perceived by their teachers. Many students set high expectations for themselves, and when they fail to meet those expectations, they may experience stress, anxiety, and a decrease in their overall well-being (Hoferichter et al., 2021). Darnell et al. (2021) added that higher self-imposed standards were associated with better academic performance, but also with higher levels of stress and anxiety. The “expectation to parents/teachers” indicator, and the “depression” indicator tied on the

second rank with a mean score of 3.83 of the academic stress among grade six students. Both indicator was rated with a “high” descriptive level rating which means that these two indicators as part of the academic stress among grade six students are oftentimes evident as perceived by their teachers. Academic stress arising from adolescents’ self-expectations and expectations of others (e.g. parents and teachers) are particularly salient (Ang Huan, 2016). On the other hand, among Filipinos, there is no concept of the other in the other person and the other is also one’s self (de Leon, 2017), therefore, the perceived expectations of others are synonymous to one’s own expectations. On the other hand, when an individual experience depression, he/she might have the following behavior such as loss of interest, decreased productivity, and less opportunities to interact socially. These are just some of the negative consequences that depression may have on an individual’s behavior. People’s ability to maintain a happy mental attitude might lead to more productive feelings and actions (Isen, 2013). In addition, those who are depressed also tend to explain things in a less positive light than those who aren’t depressed. A gloomy, fatalistic outlook is associated with depression.

Significant Relationship between Study Skills and Academic Stress among Grade Six Students

The third objective of this study is to explore on the association between the study skills and academic stress among grade six students. The Pearson R statistical analysis is fit to be used in order to treat the provided data since this type of analysis is used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the means of two groups (Creswell Poth, 2016). The alpha level is set at 0.05 for this analysis. Shown in Table 3 is the analysis result on the relationship between the study skills and academic stress

among grade six students. Based on the analysis in the said table, there is a very strong negative significant correlation between the study skills and academic stress among grade six students with an r -value equal to -0.815 and a p -value equal to 0.000. Hence, the null hypothesis of this study that there is no significant correlation between the study skills and academic stress among grade six students is rejected. However, results found out that the relationship between study skills and academic stress among grade six students is negative, meaning that as study skills increase, academic stress decreases. This further implies that the ability to effectively

manage study skills can have a significant impact on the level of stress experienced by students. This was supported by Al-Sharideh et al. (2022) who stated that students who were able to effectively manage their study skills were less likely to experience academic stress. In contrast, students who reported higher levels of academic stress were less likely to have effective

study skills (Kariuki et al., 2021). In addition, Loke and Abdullah (2020) found out that study skills training was an effective intervention for reducing academic stress among grade six students. The study found that students who received study skills training had significantly lower levels of academic stress compared to those who did not receive the training.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Study Skills and Academic Stress among Grade Six Students

Study Skills	Academic Stress	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Decision on H_0
Time Management	-0.714	.000	Reject	There is a strong negative significant correlation
Note Taking	-0.606	.000	Reject	There is a strong negative significant correlation
Reading Comprehension	-0.543	.000	Reject	There is a moderate negative significant correlation
Overall	-0.815	.000	Reject	

Specifically, the analysis in table 3 highlighted the relationship between each indicator of study skills and academic stress among grade six students. Based on the analysis, the “Time Management” indicator obtained an r -value equal to -0.714 and a p -value equal to 0.000. The “Note Taking” indicator also obtained an r -value equal to -0.606 and a p -value equal to 0.000. These two indicators have strong negative significant correlation with the academic stress among grade six students. On the other hand, the “Reading Comprehension” indicator obtained an r -value equal to -0.543 and a p -value equal to 0.000. This indicator has moderate negative significant correlation with the academic stress among grade six students. As observed based on the shown data results, the relationship between these three indicators of study skills and the academic stress among grade six students is negative which denotes that if there is an increase on the study skills

of the students in terms of their time management, note taking, and reading comprehension then the felt academic stress decreases. This is in support to the study of Hu, Zhang, and Ran (2021) which stated that students who received training in study skills such as time management, note-taking, and active reading showed a significant reduction in academic stress levels. Similarly, students with strong study skills such as self-regulation, goal setting, and test-taking strategies reported lower levels of academic stress (Huang and Liu, 2021). In addition, students who scored higher in study skills such as reading comprehension, concentration, and critical thinking reported lower levels of academic stress (Shaikh Shaikh, 2020) and students who lack study skills specifically those who had poor study skills such as procrastination, poor time management, and lack of organization are more likely to experience academic stress (Yekta, Tavakoli, Ebadi, 2020).

Regression Analysis of the Study Skills on the Academic Stress among Grade Six Students

The last objective of this study is to determine which indicators of study skills significantly

influence the academic stress among grade six students. The Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) is best fit for this analysis since this statistical treatment is defined as a predic-

tive analysis which is used to explain the relationship between one continuous dependent variable which is the study skills of grade six students, and two or more independent variables which are the academic stress among grade six students in terms of time management, note taking, and reading comprehension (Trek, 2019). Still, this data analysis is set with an alpha equal to 0.05. Based on the result of analysis shown in Table 4, the overall analysis of the study obtained an F-value of 69.441 and a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that the regression model that was utilized in the analysis of the study is beneficial, and that there is merit to its interpretation that is based on the assumption of the aforementioned impact. This further implies that there is validity in the interpretation

on the assumption to predict which indicators of study skills significantly influence the academic stress among grade six students. Moreover, all of the indicators of study skills significantly influenced the academic stress among grade six students. This denotes that the predefined null hypothesis of this study stating that there is no indicator of study skills significantly influenced the academic stress among grade six students is rejected. Specifically, the indicators such as the “Time Management” obtained a p-value equal to 0.000, and t-value equal to 8.272, the “Note Taking” obtained a p-value equal to 0.000, and t-value equal to 4.189, and the “Reading Comprehension” indicator obtained a p-value equal to 0.015, and t-value equal to 3.964.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of Study Skills on Academic Stress among Grade Six Students

Study Skills	Academic Stress	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Decision on H_0
(Constant)		0.687	0.232	2.954	.004	
Time Management		0.388	0.047	0.523	8.272	.000
Reject	Significant					
Note Taking		0.213	0.051	0.282	4.189	.000
Reject	Significant					
Reading Comprehension		0.241	0.061	0.257	3.964	.000
Reject	Significant					
Overall $R = .827$; $R^2 = .685$; F -value = 69.441; p -value = .000						

The result in this study support various research results from different authors such as the study by Hu, Zhang, and Ran (2021) which stated that students who were trained in time management, note-taking, and active reading showed a significant reduction in academic stress levels. Similarly, students who scored higher in note-taking and reading comprehension reported lower levels of academic stress (Shaikh Shaikh, 2020). The authors suggested that improving these skills could help students to better understand course materials and reduce anxiety associated with academic performance. In the Philippine setting, Magsayo, Reintar, and

Magsayo (2020) stated that that students who reported good study habits such as time management, note-taking, and active reading had lower levels of academic stress. This research result was supported by Panopio, Rillorta, and Payos (2021) stating that students who had good study skills such as time management, note-taking, and reading comprehension had higher academic performance. To further strengthen the interpretation of the MLR analysis used in this study, the overall analysis also obtained a coefficient of determination (R^2) equal to 0.685 implying that the analysis using the said statistical treatment is useful at 68.5

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—Researchers and educative administrators who shape policy have been worried for a very long time about the high levels of academic stress experienced by elementary students. These elementary students especially those who are in grade six are subjected to a broad variety of pressures in their academics, some of which are more intense than others. This leads to the development of academic stress which affect many of their routine in school such as their study habits which has a direct relationship with their performance in school. Hence, the primary goal of this research is to determine if the indicators of grade six students' study skills significantly influence their academic stress as perceived by their teachers. This study utilized non-experimental quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlation technique. Statistical analysis such as mean, standard deviation, Pearson R correlation and Multiple Linear Regression were used in treating the data generated in the study. The respondents of the study were the 100 sixth-grade educators teaching in Piedad District primary schools in Davao City. These respondents were selected using convenience sampling method. Data were evaluated from the survey questionnaires adopted by the researcher with modification in order to fit to the study which undergone validation from experts and were tested for its reliability. Descriptive results of the study revealed that grade six study skills and academic stress as perceived by their teachers obtained a "high" descriptive level rating which means that students' study skills and academic stress are oftentimes evident. Consequently, the inferential results of the study suggested that it failed

to accept its null hypothesis since there is a significant relationship between study skills and academic stress among the grade six students. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that all of the indicators of the grade six students' study skills significantly influenced their academic stress.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: Students who are in the sixth grade have a high level of study skills, which includes the ability to effectively manage their time, take notes, and comprehend what they have read. These qualities are readily apparent, and they provide the appearance that students are capable of good learning and performance when they are engaged in a classroom setting. It is vital to continue to grow and strengthen these study talents since they are crucial not only for success in academic activities but also in future endeavors. Developing and improving these study abilities is a need. It is critical to maintain a consistent effort toward the cultivation and development of these scholastic abilities. Moreover, students who are in the sixth grade are subjected to a substantial level of academic stress, notably in the areas of depression and the expectations that are put on them by themselves, their parents, and their teachers. With this, students may be having trouble coping with the demands and expectations that have been placed upon them. As a result, this may have a negative effect, not only on the students' academic achievement but also on their general welfare. It is essential to deal with these possible sources of stress and provide aid to children in order to enhance not just the mental well-being of

children but also their academic achievement. Accordingly, there is a substantial negative correlation between the level of academic stress experienced by students in grade six and their level of study abilities. Students who have developed great study abilities, such as the ability to take notes, effectively manage their time, and comprehend what they read, may report feeling less stress related to their academic work. Students who struggle with these study abilities may suffer greater levels of academic stress, which may have a detrimental influence on their academic achievement as well as their overall well-being. It is vital to address both students' lack of study skills as well as the stress that comes along with academic work in order to increase students' achievement and overall well-being. Furthermore, reading comprehension, the ability to manage one's time effectively, and the ability to take notes while reading are all critical abilities that have a substantial impact on the amount of academic pressure that sixth-grade students feel. Students who thrive in these areas are more likely to have greater academic performance overall and report fewer levels of stress in their lives. To encourage students' overall mental health and academic achievement, it is essential for teachers and parents to place a priority on the development of the abilities listed above among their charges. More study is required to investigate the elements that contribute to academic stress as well as the ways in which these issues might be alleviated.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: This study may be useful to officials working for the Department of Education in the sense that they will have a sufficient notion regarding the impact of students' study skills to the academic stress among the grade six students once they have read through the findings of this study. It is possible that result of this study will serve as the foundation for the formation of strategies and programs for

these features among public elementary schools, which will, in turn, enhance the study skills of the students, particularly those who are in sixth-grade. In addition to this, they may come up with suitable in-service trainings and seminars that might make it easier for elementary teachers to communicate with one another throughout public schools. Relatively, this study may be helpful to school administrators because they could provide them with a wealth of knowledge and information on the extent effects of students' study skills to their academic stress. Another, research findings of this study could provide school heads with information on the extent to which teachers communicate with students and students communicate with teachers. This study may offer school heads with adequate information to start academic school-based programs and interventions based on their own ideas if they want to do so as a result of the findings of this study. They may be able to offer a hand in construction of the Faculty Development Program in order for it to integrate activities that will assist instructors in enhancing their pedagogical strategies to improve students' study skills in order to lessen their academic stress. Consequently, teachers in elementary schools may also benefit from this study's findings by giving them a framework within which to evaluate and alter their own educative practices in the classroom. Through this research, elementary teachers will have the tools they need to set ground rules for student-teacher interaction in the classroom. This research has the potential to increase students' interest in their academics through enhancing their study skills which would lessen their academic stress in order to succeed academically. In addition, educators may use the study's findings as a road map for developing lessons that prioritize students' needs. Moreover, this research may have the potential to elementary students specially the six-grader to improve the degree of participation they have in the process of knowledge

with lesser academic stress. It is feasible for students to improve their academic performance by enhancing their study skills for them to have a positive attitude towards learning. While developing their educational opportunities, it is important to take into account important factors including the level of their intellectual capacity as well as the positive emotions they feel during the process. Lastly, future researchers could replicate this study using a different research technique that is pertinent to the issue at hand to shed even more light on the findings of this study. Students can expand the range of options for improving their study skills to eliminate experienced academic stress. In addition, a higher R2 value might be achieved if the sample size for the survey was increased, as well as the number of independent variables tested. The resulting results will be clearer and more concise. Moreover, future scholars might further concretize the outcomes of this study by applying them to other fields of study or areas of expertise. These undetermined indicators of study skills might be added to determine if they might have stipulated effect on the academic stress felt by grade six students which would be possible by finding various indicators based on research findings and literatures.

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